

Aftermath interventions of Hurricane Melissa in Jamaica, 2025.

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Jamaica, a small island developing state (SIDS) in the Caribbean, remains highly vulnerable to a wide range of natural disasters, including hurricanes, earthquakes, floods, and droughts. The Inter-American Development Bank (IDB) estimates that between 1970 and 2020, Jamaica suffered over US\$2 billion in direct damage from natural disasters. (1). Hurricanes, and their midlatitude relative, extratropical cyclones, are the most powerful storms on Earth among the most deadly and costly of natural hazards. (2-3). As at 8pm local time on 27 October, a hurricane warning remained in effect for the country, with Hurricane Melissa remaining a Category 5¹ hurricane. The hurricane made landfall in Jamaica on 28 October. The entire country was declared to be a threatened area, under Order pursuant to section 26(2) of the Disaster Risk Management Act. (4). The effects associated with the hurricane impact as 29th October, 2025, 3 deaths, 12 injured, 0 missing, N/A evacuated. (5) with a population approx. 2.8 m potentially exposed. (6)

Figure 1: NHC Forecast Track for Hurricane Melissa and its landfall to Jamaica Island on the 27st October, 2025

This assignment proposes a low framework for emergency intervention, outlining income-outputs, and income indicators, data sources, and response activities after the impact of Hurricane Melissa with Jamaica’s emergency response capacities.

Public Health Intervention Framework after the impact of Hurricane Melissa in Jamaica.

Intervention Concept

To strengthen community health systems and surveillance mechanisms to ensure the continuity of essential services, prevent communicable disease outbreaks, and promote population well-being (7) in the post-hurricane period.

Objetives

- Restore access to clean water, and healthcare.
- Track if any disease surveillance and outbreak response.
- Address mental health and psychosocial needs.
- Improve information management and intersectoral coordination through DMIS.

Input Indicators and Data Sources		
Indicator	Description	Where to obtain the data
Health facilities damaged	Rate (%) of hospitals/clinics affected	Ministry of Health and Wellness Jamaica https://www.moh.gov.jm/
Access to clean water	Rate (%) of regions/municipalities/communities with access to potable (tap/drinking) water.	The Water Resources Authority (WRA) https://www.wra.gov.jm/
EMTs ⁱⁱ available	Number (#) of health workers on call	Ministry of Health and Wellness Jamaica https://www.moh.gov.jm/

Proposed response activities to mitigate other possible related-hazards

- Conduct rapid health and infrastructure assessments using DMIS tools.
- Restore primary health care services and temporary clinics.
- Provide emergency WASH (Water, Sanitation, Hygiene) supplies and vector control measures.
- Establish mental health and psychosocial support programs.
- Strengthen disease surveillance and laboratory reporting systems.
- Conduct community health education and hygiene promotion campaigns.

Output Indicators and Data Sources		
Indicator	Description	Where to obtain the data
Health facilities functioning	Rate (%) of hospitals/clinics being operational post-intervention.	World Health Organization https://www.who.int/ and Pan American Health Organization https://www.paho.org/en
Access to clean water	Rate (%) of affected population with clean water	Wash Cluster https://www.washcluster.net/about-us
Disease outbreak alerts	Number (#) of alerts within 24/48 hours	World Health Organization https://www.who.int/ and Pan American Health Organization https://www.paho.org/en

Outcome Indicators and Data Sources		
Indicator	Description	Where to obtain the data
Morbidity / Mortality	Rate (%) decrease in cases of cholera, dengue, and fatalities.	World Health Organization https://www.who.int/ and Pan American Health Organization https://www.paho.org/en
Improve mental health	Rate (%) decrease cases in distress or trauma symptoms	Ministry of Health and Wellness Jamaica https://www.moh.gov.jm/

Expected Impact

The implementation of this proposed framework will reduce the risk of post-disaster disease outbreaks, as well it will restore essential health services to recovery, and strengthen Jamaica’s resilience to future emergencies. (8-9).

Conclusion

The aftermath of Hurricane Melissa, a Category 5 storm, which significantly battered Jamaica underscores the need for a structured, data-informed approach to public health intervention. Applying a low-level framework within the DMIS context allows for efficient

coordination, prioritization, and monitoring of emergency health activities. Building capacity for rapid data collection and information sharing is essential to sustain resilience and reduce health vulnerabilities in disaster-prone regions such as Jamaica.

References

1. Bourne PA, Foster C. *Planning for the next natural disaster in Jamaica: a strategic framework for resilience and risk reduction*. Kingston (JM): Vocational Training Development Institute; 2025.
2. Keller EA, Blodgett RH. *Natural hazards: Earth's processes as hazards, disasters, and catastrophes*. 2nd ed. Upper Saddle River (NJ): Pearson Prentice Hall; 2006.
3. Fielding WJ, Nair V, Glenn-Callender J, Morris L, Ballance V. *Hurricane Dorian: the response of University of The Bahamas, August to December 2019 – a case study for discussion*. Nassau (BS): University of The Bahamas; 2019.
4. A situation report from Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) for Jamaica: "Situation Report 2 Jamaica - Hurricane Melissa 28 Oct 2025"
5. Ministry of Health and Wellness HEOC report #5
6. Statistical Institute of Jamaica data
7. Sphere Association. *Humanitarian charter and minimum standards in humanitarian response*. 2018 ed. Geneva: Sphere Association; 2018.
8. Ministry of Health and Wellness (Jamaica). *National Health Emergency and Disaster Management Plan*. Kingston: MoH; 2022.
9. World Health Organization (WHO). *Health Cluster Guide: Humanitarian Health Coordination in Emergencies*. Geneva: WHO; 2019.

ⁱ Category Five Hurricane: The Saffir-Simpson Hurricane Scale

Winds greater than 249 km (155 mi.) per hour; Storm surge generally greater than 5.5 m (18 ft.) above normal. Complete roof failure on many residences and industrial buildings. Some complete building failures with small utility buildings blown over or away. All shrubs, trees, and signs blown down. Complete destruction of mobile homes. Severe and extensive window and door damage. Low-lying escape routes are cut off by rising water 3 to 5 hours before arrival of the hurricane center. Major damage to lower floors of all structures located less than 4.6 m (15 ft.) above sea level and within 458 m (500 yards) of the shoreline. Massive evacuation of residential areas on low ground within 8 to 16 km (5 to 10 mi) of the shore may be required.

ⁱⁱ Emergency Medical Teams